

Integer Partition Function in Nonrecursive Form and Related Results

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(Dated: October 28, 2017)

A nonrecursive, finite, exact integer partition function $p(n)$ is presented in terms of elementary functions, solving a problem that has persisted since Euler wrote about partitions in 1753.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1038438

I. INTRODUCTION AND MAIN RESULT

The integer partition function $p(n)$ is the number of ways of writing n as a sum of positive integers, treating different summand orders as equivalent. For example,

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} 4 = 4 \\ 4 = 3 + 1 \\ 4 = 2 + 2 \\ 4 = 2 + 1 + 1 \\ 4 = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow p(4) = 5, \quad (1)$$

so for $n = 4$, there are 5 ways to write 4 as a sum of positive integers. By this definition, $p(n < 0) = 0$, and by convention $p(0) \equiv 1$. For example, the values of $p(n)$ from $n = 0$ to $n = 30$ are 1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 15, 22, 30, 42, 56, 77, 101, 135, 176, 231, 297, 385, 490, 627, 792, 1002, 1255, 1575, 1958, 2436, 3010, 3718, 4565, 5604.

The integer partition function $p(n)$ is an important part of combinatorics, appearing in generalizations of the Twelfthfold Way [1–13], and is therefore also important in statistics and its many applications.

Euler's work on $p(n)$ yielded the recursive formula [14, 15] (modified here to accept all integers n),

$$p(n) = \delta_{n,0} + \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k+1} [p(q_{n,k}^+) + p(q_{n,k}^-)], \quad (2)$$

where $q_{n,k}^{\pm} \equiv n - \frac{1}{2}k(3k \pm 1)$ and $\delta_{a,b}$ is the Kronecker delta. While (2) is correct, its recursive form and the tantalizingly simple definition of integer partitions has led many to attempt a closed-form solution.

Ramanujan and Hardy [16] found several large- n asymptotic expressions for $p(n)$, as did Uspensky [17] and Rademacher [18]. In 2011, Malenfant [19] found a finite but expanding sum for $p(n)$ in terms of multinomial coefficients, and also in 2011, Bruinier and Ono [20] found a finite sum for $p(n)$ in terms of derivatives of functions of Eisenstein series and Dedekind eta functions.

Here, we give a relatively simple expression for $p(n)$ as

$$p(n) = \frac{4^n \sum_{m=0}^{n^2} \sum_{l=0}^{2n} \prod_{k=1}^{2n} e^{i \frac{\pi m(n-2k+3)}{2(n^2+1)}} \cos\left(\pi \left[\frac{m(k-1)}{n^2+1} + \frac{l}{2n+1} \right]\right)}{(n^2+1)(2n+1)}, \quad (3)$$

for all integers n , where Sec. II gives a full derivation of this result. This function is *nonrecursive*, *exact* (not merely an approximation), and it is *finite*, up to the elementary unit-complex exponentials and the cosine.

As shown in App. A, (3) can be implemented symbolically to yield the *exact* value of $p(n)$ for all n . Unfortunately, the exact symbolic method of App. A is generally slower than Euler's method, scaling as $O(4^n)$.

Furthermore, as with all equations, simply numerically evaluating (3) on a typical machine with 16-digit precision causes rounding errors for $n \geq 29$, even though (3) is exact. In principle, symbolic software with numerical precision control can be used to reduce rounding errors and obtain the correct $p(n)$ up to the overflow limit of any machine. However, since (3) scales as $O(n^4)$ numerically, it is unlikely to be faster than Euler's recursive method for large n , even though it *is* faster than Euler's method until rounding error becomes significant. Perhaps (3) can be shown to simplify to a function of fewer terms.

Nevertheless, the nonrecursive, compact form of (3) for the exact value of $p(n)$ provides a satisfying conclusion to a problem that has persisted for many years.

II. DERIVATION OF MAIN RESULTS

To prove (3), first we start with a few useful facts:

1. Given any finite polynomial,

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^k, \quad (4)$$

discrete Fourier orthogonality yields its coefficients as

$$c_k = \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} mk} f(e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} m}), \quad (5)$$

as proved in App. B.

2. The partition problem can be generalized as

$$\begin{aligned} p(n) &\equiv \text{the number of partitions of } n \text{ objects} \\ p_k(n) &\equiv \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{the number of partitions of } n \text{ objects} \\ \text{into exactly } k \text{ parts} \end{array} \right) \\ p(N, M, n) &\equiv \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{the number of partitions of } n \text{ objects} \\ \text{into at most } M \text{ parts} \\ \text{each of size at most } N \end{array} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where a *part* is a group of objects, and the *size* of a part is the number of objects it contains, and where

$$\sum_{n=0}^{MN} p(N, M, n) q^n = \binom{M+N}{M}_q, \quad (7)$$

where $\binom{n}{k}_q$ is the Gaussian binomial coefficient (or q -binomial coefficient) [21–23], given by

$$\binom{n}{k}_q = \prod_{r=0}^{k-1} \frac{q^{n-r} - 1}{q^{k-r} - 1}, \quad (8)$$

for $n \in 0, \dots, \infty$ and $k \in 0, \dots, n$, where q is not allowed to be certain roots of unity *in this formula*. In cases where $k > n$ or $n < 0$, $\binom{n}{k}_q = 0$.

3. The q -binomial theorem [22] is

$$\prod_{j=1}^n (1 + q^{j-1}x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}_q q^{\frac{k(k-1)}{2}} x^k. \quad (9)$$

Now we have enough information to solve for $p(n)$, and to do so we adopt a theorem-proof format.

Theorem 1: From the definitions in (6), $p(n)$ and $p_k(n)$ are special cases of $p(N, M, n)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} p(n) &= p(n, n, n) \\ p_k(n) &= (1 - \text{sgn}(n)\delta_{k,0})p(n, k, n) \\ &\quad - (1 - \text{sgn}(n)(\delta_{k,0} + \delta_{k,1}))p(n, k-1, n). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Proof: By the definition of $p(N, M, n)$ in (6), $p(n, n, n)$ is the number of partitions of n objects into at most n parts each of size at most n . That exactly describes $p(n)$ because $p(n)$ considers all possible partitions of n up to n parts with each part having up to size n . Therefore $p(n) = p(n, n, n)$.

For example, in (1), the number of parts M ranges from 1 in the top line to 4 in the bottom line, and the size of each part N ranges from 4 units in the first line down to 1 unit each in the bottom line.

For $p_k(n)$, which is the number of partitions of n objects into exactly k parts, there is no restriction on the size of each part, so we can add the phrase “each up to size n ” referring to the allowable size of each of the k parts. That sets $N = n$ in $p(N, M, n)$. The “exactly k parts” of $p_k(n)$ means that $p(n, k, n)$ considers too many options since it means the number of partitions of n objects into *at most* k parts each of size at most n . To get *exactly* k parts we need to subtract from $p(n, k, n)$ the cumulative sum of everything up to $k-1$ parts which is $p(n, k-1, n)$, so that, if $n, k \geq 2$ to avoid the initial cases, $p(n, k, n) - p(n, k-1, n)$ counts the number of partitions of n objects into exactly k parts each up to size n , which means $p_k(n) = p(n, k, n) - p(n, k-1, n)$ for $n, k \geq 2$. For the initial cases, from (7) and (8), $n \leq MN$ becomes $n \leq kn$ and $M \leq M+N$ becomes $k \leq k+n$ for $p(n, k, n)$, and for $p(n, k-1, n)$ they become $n \leq (k-1)n$ and $k \leq k+n$. Thus $p(n, k, n)$ needs to vanish when $n \neq 0$ and $k = 0$, and $p(n, k-1, n)$ needs to vanish when $n \neq 0$ and $k = 0, 1$, which explains the factors in (10).

For example, $p_2(4) = 2$ in (1) since there are two ways $\{\{3, 1\}, \{2, 2\}\}$ to partition $n = 4$ into exactly $k = 2$ parts where each part’s size can range from 1

to 4. Meanwhile $p(4, 2, 4) = 3$ since there are three ways $\{\{4\}, \{3, 1\}, \{2, 2\}\}$ to partition $n = 4$ into at most $k = 2$ parts regardless of part size, and $p(4, 1, 4) = 1$ since there is one way $\{\{4\}\}$ to partition $n = 4$ into at most $k = 1$ part. Thus, $p(4, 2, 4) - p(4, 1, 4) = 3 - 1 = 2 = p_2(4)$.

We could also use the fact that $p(n) = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k(n)$, but the first line in (10) is simpler.

Theorem 2: The q -binomial coefficients can be expressed to accept any root of unity in q as

$$\binom{n}{k}_q = \frac{1}{(n+1)q^{\frac{k(k-1)}{2}}} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i\frac{2\pi mk}{n+1}} \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + q^{j-1}e^{-i\frac{2\pi m}{n+1}}). \quad (11)$$

Proof: (11) is obtained by applying (5) to (9) with $f(x) \equiv \prod_{j=1}^n (1 + q^{j-1}x)$ and $c_k \equiv \binom{n}{k}_q q^{k(k-1)/2}$, and then solving for $\binom{n}{k}_q$. See also App. C.

Theorem 3: $p(N, M, n)$ can be expressed as

$$p(N, M, n) = \frac{1}{MN+1} \sum_{m=0}^{MN} e^{i\frac{2\pi mn}{MN+1}} \binom{M+N}{M}_e^{-i\frac{2\pi m}{MN+1}}. \quad (12)$$

Proof: Apply (4) and (5) to (7), by setting $x \rightarrow q$, $n \rightarrow MN$, $k \rightarrow n$, $f(q) \equiv \binom{M+N}{M}_q$, and $c_n \equiv p(N, M, n)$. Since Theorem 2 showed that roots of unity are permissible as input for q in forms such as (11), then (12) is valid.

Theorem 4: A closed form for $p(N, M, n)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} p(N, M, n) &= \frac{\sum_{m=0}^{MN} e^{i\frac{\pi m[2n+M(M-1)]}{MN+1}} \sum_{l=0}^{M+N} e^{i\frac{2\pi lM}{M+N+1}}}{(MN+1)(M+N+1)} \\ &\quad \times \prod_{j=1}^{M+N} \left(1 + e^{-i2\pi \left[\frac{m(j-1)}{MN+1} + \frac{l}{M+N+1} \right]} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Proof: Use $n = M+N$ and $k = M$ in (11) to get $\binom{M+N}{M}_q$ with $q = e^{-i2\pi m/(MN+1)}$ and put the result into (12).

Theorem 5: Closed forms for $p(n)$ are

$$p(n) = \frac{\sum_{m=0}^{n^2} e^{i\frac{\pi mn(n+1)}{n^2+1}} \sum_{l=0}^{2n} e^{i\frac{2\pi ln}{2n+1}} \prod_{j=1}^{2n} \left(1 + e^{-i2\pi \left[\frac{m(j-1)}{n^2+1} + \frac{l}{2n+1} \right]} \right)}{(n^2+1)(2n+1)}, \quad (14)$$

and its simplified form,

$$p(n) = \frac{4^n \sum_{m=0}^{n^2} \sum_{l=0}^{2n} \prod_{k=1}^{2n} e^{i\frac{\pi m(n-2k+3)}{2(n^2+1)}} \cos\left(\pi \left[\frac{m(k-1)}{n^2+1} + \frac{l}{2n+1} \right]\right)}{(n^2+1)(2n+1)}, \quad (15)$$

Proof: By Theorem 1, set $N = n$ and $M = n$ in (13) to get (14). Then move all roots of unity inside the product and simplify to get (15) which gives (3).

Theorem 6: A closed form for $p_k(n)$ is

$$\begin{aligned}
p_k(n) = & a_{n,k} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{kn} \sum_{l=0}^{k+n} \frac{e^{i \frac{\pi m[2n+k(k-1)]}{kn+1}} e^{i \frac{2\pi l k}{k+n+1}}}{(kn+1)(k+n+1)} \right. \\
& \times \prod_{j=1}^{k+n} \left(1 + e^{-i2\pi \left[\frac{m(j-1)}{kn+1} + \frac{l}{k+n+1} \right]} \right) \left. \right\} \\
& - b_{n,k} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^{(k-1)n} \sum_{l=0}^{k-1+n} \frac{e^{i \frac{\pi m[2n+(k-1)(k-2)]}{(k-1)n+1}} e^{i \frac{2\pi l(k-1)}{k+n}}}{((k-1)n+1)(k+n)} \right. \\
& \times \prod_{j=1}^{k-1+n} \left(1 + e^{-i2\pi \left[\frac{m(j-1)}{(k-1)n+1} + \frac{l}{k+n} \right]} \right) \left. \right\}, \tag{16}
\end{aligned}$$

with $a_{n,k} \equiv 1 - \text{sgn}(n)\delta_{k,0}$ and $b_{n,k} \equiv 1 - \text{sgn}(n)(\delta_{k,0} + \delta_{k,1})$.

Proof: By Theorem 1, calculate $p_k(n) = a_{n,k}p(n, k, n) - b_{n,k}p(n, k-1, n)$ using (13). Note that (16) obeys the requirements that $p_0(0) = 1$, $p_{k \leq 0}(n > 0) = 0$, and $p_{k > 0}(n \leq 0) = 0$, and sum limits prevent division by 0.

III. SOME RELATED RESULTS

Here we briefly list some results related in the senses that the same Fourier orthogonality method was applied to obtain them, and they have combinatorial significance.

In all cases below, we omit explicit derivation since they are mainly just applications of (5). Furthermore, though each result is *exact*, they will all suffer from the same kinds of rounding errors when implemented on typical machines. Again, this need not be the case if careful symbolic methods are used to properly handle unit-complex numbers without numerical approximations, as in App. A.

Theorem 7: New forms of the binomial coefficient:

$$\begin{aligned}
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} mk} (1 + e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} m})^n \\
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{2^n}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i \frac{\pi m(2k-n)}{n+1}} \cos^n\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right) \\
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{2^n}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n \cos\left(\frac{\pi m(2k-n)}{n+1}\right) \cos^n\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right), \tag{17}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{(-1)^k}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} mk} (1 - e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} m})^n \\
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{(-1)^k (2i)^n}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n e^{i \frac{\pi m(2k-n)}{n+1}} \sin^n\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right) \\
\binom{n}{k} &= \frac{(-1)^k 2^n}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n \cos\left(\pi \left[\frac{m(2k-n)}{n+1} + \frac{n}{2} \right]\right) \sin^n\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right). \tag{18}
\end{aligned}$$

Through these results we can obtain a large number of other results, anywhere binomial coefficients are used. Examples include Stirling numbers of the first and second kinds, Eulerian numbers, Bernoulli numbers, Bell numbers, Catalan numbers, harmonic numbers, and anywhere such numbers are used or related, such as with Bernoulli numbers and the Riemann zeta function. In

some cases, use of (5) will require roots of unity as input to the binomial coefficient, and in that case one can simply use falling factorials to handle it.

We could also use these results to represent $\binom{n}{k}$ as an inner product, such as

$$\binom{n}{k} = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}; \quad \begin{aligned} a_m &\equiv \frac{1}{n+1} \cos\left(\frac{\pi m(2k-n)}{n+1}\right) \\ b_m &\equiv [2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right)]^n, \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

for $m \in 0, \dots, n$, $\mathbf{c} \equiv (c_0, \dots, c_n)^T$, and $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} \equiv \sum_{m=0}^n a_m b_m$.

We could use similar methods to write (3) and all other results in terms of matrix multiplication of vectors and matrices, but there is no computational advantage in doing so, and the explicit nature of the given equations makes it easier to see that they are nonrecursive.

Theorem 8: Partial sums of the binomial coefficient on its bottom index can be expressed as

$$\sum_{j=0}^k \binom{n}{j} = \frac{2^n}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n \cos^n\left(\frac{\pi m}{n+1}\right) \sum_{j=0}^k \cos\left(\frac{\pi m(2j-n)}{n+1}\right). \tag{20}$$

This is another unsolved problem now solved exactly, with its numerical implementation subject to the same rounding-error difficulties in spite of its exactness.

Furthermore, we can use (17) or (18) to express *any* sum of *any function* of $\binom{n}{k}$ in a potentially convergent way. For example, we could obtain general and unusual quantities such as $\sum_{m=a}^b \sum_{j=c}^d \binom{m}{j}^x$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented several new results for computing the integer partition function $p(n)$ and related quantities. These results are all exact and nonrecursive. Unfortunately, numerical implementation of them in standard machines can introduce significant rounding error, limiting their usefulness. However, careful symbolic handling does permit exact computation, though it comes at the price of increased computation time.

Therefore, unless further simplifications can be found or better algorithms can be developed to compute equations such as (3) exactly, these formulas are mainly theoretical novelties. Nevertheless, such advances may be possible in the future, making these results potentially much faster than their traditional counterparts.

The integer partition function $p(n)$ is not merely an intellectual curiosity, but has many applications in physics and engineering, giving us practical reasons to study it. Therefore this achievement of a compact, nonrecursive closed-form expression for $p(n)$ may be a valuable puzzle-piece to understanding many physical phenomena. Furthermore, the solution methods used here are simple and general enough that they may have applications in a wide range of areas, and it is hoped that they will be found useful to the interested reader.

Appendix A: Method to Get Exact Results

While Sec. II *proves* that (3) and its related results are *exact*, this may not be obvious to all readers, and not all symbolic engines accomplish the simplification unaided. Here we describe a method that actually computed (3) exactly for any n with popular symbolic software.

First, after choosing an actual integer for n , define symbols $m, l, \omega_a, \omega_b, S_a, S_b$. Then make

$$A = S_a S_b \omega_a^{\frac{mn(n+1)}{2}} \omega_b^{ln} \prod_{k=1}^{2n} (1 + \omega_a^{-m(k-1)} \omega_b^{-l}). \quad (\text{A1})$$

Next, expand, convert A to a string A_S , and parse it for each term, using $+$ as a delimiter, and then stop and keep only the term that does not contain an ω character. This parsing enforces the fact that $\sum_{k=0}^{q-1} \omega_q^{jk} = q \delta_{\text{mod}(j,q),0}$ for roots of unity $\omega_q \equiv e^{\pm i 2\pi/q}$. In this case, it enforces $S_a \omega_a^{hm} = 0$ and $S_b \omega_b^{jl} = 0$, where $\omega_a = e^{i 2\pi/(n^2+1)}$, $\omega_b = e^{i 2\pi/(2n+1)}$, $S_a = \sum_{m=0}^{n^2}$, and $S_b = \sum_{l=0}^{2n}$. The only terms that do not vanish are those that have no ω in them since the numerical multiples shown here as h and j in the expansion do not activate the $\delta_{\text{mod}(j,q),0}$ of the identity, and if the symbolic engine has already grouped terms, the parsing result is $A'_S = p(n) \times S_a \times S_b$, where $p(n)$ is not a symbol here but represents the number that appears in the parsing result string.

Then, the facts $\sum_{m=0}^{n^2} 1 = n^2 + 1$ and $\sum_{l=0}^{2n} 1 = 2n + 1$ can be implemented simply by converting A'_S back to a symbolic object and substituting $S_a = 1$ and $S_b = 1$, and ignoring the denominator of (3). The result is exactly $p(n)$ with no rounding error.

Appendix B: Derivation of the Discrete Fourier Extraction Formula

Here our goal is to show how to extract coefficients c_k from polynomials $f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^k$ as in (4), *without* resorting to solving for the roots of $f(x)$ or integration. Therefore our first step is to find some orthogonality relation that would let us achieve this (based on [24]).

Recall that the defining property of a unitary operator U is $U^\dagger = U^{-1}$, which leads to $U^\dagger U = I$ where I is the identity, and has matrix-element form

$$\sum_{j=1}^n U_{j,k}^* U_{j,l} = \delta_{k,l}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

where $\delta_{k,l}$ is the Kronecker delta.

Since our only available means of inserting an index-dependent quantity in $f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n c_k x^k$ is through x , and it appears as x^k in the sum, that means that whatever orthogonal functions we choose need to have some clear orthogonality relation when raised to integer powers. In general, unitary operators do not allow this, however *discrete Fourier* operators *exactly* satisfy it, since all of their elements are proportional to roots of unity.

The n -level discrete Fourier matrix has elements

$$F_{j,l} \equiv F_{j,l}^{[n]} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n} (j-1)(l-1)} \quad \text{for } j, l \in 1, \dots, n, \quad (\text{B2})$$

and being unitary, satisfies (B.1) as $\sum_{j=1}^n F_{j,k}^* F_{j,l} = \delta_{k,l}$. Since our sum of interest has $n + 1$ terms with an index starting on zero, put $n \rightarrow n + 1$, and $j \rightarrow j + 1$, so that the discrete Fourier orthonormality relation is

$$\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{j=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jk} e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jl} = \delta_{k,l}, \quad (\text{B3})$$

where we have left the exponents unsimplified to be suggestive of what comes next.

Now we calculate $f(e^{-i 2\pi j/(n+1)})$ where we use new summation index h as $f(x) = \sum_{h=0}^n c_h x^h$, and then multiply through by $e^{i 2\pi jk/(n+1)}$, sum over j from 0 to n , and scale by $\frac{1}{n+1}$, which lets us use (B.3) to extract the coefficients as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=0}^n c_h e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jh} &= f(e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} j}) \\ e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jk} \sum_{h=0}^n c_h e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jh} &= e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jk} f(e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} j}) \\ \sum_{h=0}^n c_h \delta_{k,h} &= \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{j=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jk} f(e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} j}) \\ c_k &= \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{j=0}^n e^{i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} jk} f(e^{-i \frac{2\pi}{n+1} j}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B4})$$

which gives us the result in (5), where we summed over j and used (B.3) in going from line 2 to line 3 in (B.4).

Appendix C: Alternative Proof that Roots of Unity Are Acceptable for q in the q -Binomial Coefficient

The fact that q can be any root of unity in $\binom{n}{k}_q$ can also be established by the recursion formula [22],

$$\binom{n}{k}_q = \sum_{j=k-1}^{n-1} q^{j-(k-1)} \binom{j}{k-1}_q, \quad (\text{C1})$$

starting with the fact that $\binom{n}{0}_q = 1$, which, after repeated application, yields

$$\binom{n_{k+1}}{k}_q = \prod_{r=1}^k \left(\sum_{n_{k-r+1}=k-r}^{n_{k-r+2}-1} q^{n_{k-r+1}-(k-r)} \right), \quad (\text{C2})$$

for $k \leq n_{k+1}$, where $n_{k+1} \equiv n$. This shows that there is no problem with q being a root of unity, and that the restriction against that in (8) is merely due to that form.

Note that although we could have used (C.2) instead of (11), (C.2) is inherently recursive, which is evident since it scales as $O(n!)$, whereas (11) is not recursive and only scales as $O(n^2)$ numerically.

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